

**RESEARCH OF TECHNOGENIC WASTES OF SOME MINING
ENTERPRISES IN UZBEKISTAN****Asadjon Kambarov**

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Abstract. The results of X-ray fluorescence and atomic emission analyzes of technogenic raw materials of mining production at CS AMMC JSC and GMC No. 2 at NMMC JSC of the Republic of Uzbekistan are considered, which showed the content of non-ferrous metals such as gold, silver, copper, zinc, chromium, manganese and others.

Key words: X-ray fluorescence analysis, atomic emission analysis, non-ferrous metals, industrial waste.

Introduction. The main reason for the relatively low level of use of the deposit's raw materials is that while the extracted rock mass usually contains several useful components, mining and metallurgical enterprises are programmed to produce the vast majority of only one type of marketable product. Therefore, significant reserves of mineral raw materials accumulate in dumps. In this regard, increasing the efficiency of existing technologies for complex processing of polymetallic ores containing platinum group metals (PGMs) and developing new options for their processing is important. The mining and metallurgical industry of Uzbekistan is one of the important sectors of

development, which is unthinkable without the development and implementation of improved and new technologies for processing mineral raw materials, in particular polymetallic ores, for the purpose of comprehensive extraction of valuable components.

Relevance of the problem. According to experts, the practical implementation of already developed technical solutions for the development of technogenic deposits will reduce the volume of mineral extraction by 20-30%.

Instruments and reagents. High-performance energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometer – Rigaku NEX CG EDXRF Analyzer with Polarization in set – 9022 19 000 Japan; Optical emission spectrometer with inductively coupled plasma ICPE-9000 “Shimadzu”, Kyoto Japan; concentrated solution of sulfuric acid H₂SO₄. beaker, flask, test tubes and pipette.

The discussion of the results. X-ray fluorescence analysis of samples of CS sludge showed that the most iron in its composition is 58.2%, followed by silicon 23% and aluminum 6.5%. There are also many other elements that are of great importance for the national economy, such as: magnesium (Mg), sulfur (S), calcium (Ca), potassium (K), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), etc. The study of technogenic raw materials of GMC-2 using this method showed that the composition contains significant amounts of precious metals: 1.02 g/t silver and 0.501 g/t gold, as well as copper 48.9 g/t, zinc 66.7 g/t, uranium 2.53 g/t, chromium 70.9 g/t, nickel 43.4 g/t and others.

Pic. 1. The most common elements in % (GMC-2)

The MMC-2 sludge contains a significant amount of aluminum 28%, iron 20%, potassium 15%, sodium 10%, titanium 2% and others.

Experimental part. Average monthly samples of copper waste (sludge) from the Almalyk mining and metallurgical plant, as shown by X-ray fluorescence analysis, contain the following components - Fe_2O_3 , SiO_2 , CaO , MgO , ZnO and CuO . An atomic emission spectroscope with inductively coupled plasma made it clear that in samples of technogenic raw materials from Hydrometallurgical Plant No. 2 NMMC, per ton of technogenic raw materials there are: 1.02 g of Ag; 0.501 g Au; 48.9 g Cu; 66.7 g Zn; 328 g Mn. When preparing samples of sludge from MPZ AGMK and GMZ-2, it was necessary to dissolve it in an aggressive environment, having previously crushed it into powder. An example of an aggressive environment in which the sample was dissolved is concentrated sulfuric acid. When dissolved in a strong acid, the main part of the metals included in the sludge and pulp goes into solution. By spraying the solution in an atomic emission spectrometer, we transfer metal ions to an excited state, so we determined the qualitative and quantitative composition of the sample under study.

Conclusions

During the study of samples of technogenic raw materials from non-ferrous metallurgy enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a significant content of important non-ferrous metals was revealed. X-ray fluorescence analysis of slag samples showed that the most iron in its composition is 58.2%, followed by silicon 23% and aluminum 6.5%. There are also many other elements that are of great importance for the national economy, such as: magnesium (Mg), sulfur (S), calcium (Ca), potassium (K), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn) and many others. AMMC smelter as the main component of building materials. Based on the concept of solving problems of waste processing and the proposed management of the mineral resource base of the mining and processing industry, a forecast has been developed for the involvement of technogenic raw materials in the processing of technogenic raw materials at the 2nd hydrometallurgical plant (HMZ-2). The forecast shows that if in 2010 the share of low-quality mineral raw materials in the processing of GMZ-2 was 44.1 percent, then by 2035 the volume of processing of technogenic raw materials will increase to 88.0 percent.

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